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A STUDY TO IDENTIFY THE COMMONALITIES AMONG THE VARIOUS FDT MODELS FOR DEVELOPING BEST FITTED MODEL FOR HIGHER EDUCATION ACADEMICIANS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to provide the wider context for the investigation of Faculty Development Training's Models and Approaches. This study accentuates to identify the various Training Models, can be utilised to train the Higher Education Academicians. The main intention of this particular study is to review all the models which were developed to train the teachers teaching professional students with a view to augment their Pedagogic Skills. An extensive literature survey was conducted to identify all the suitable models which can be implemented for training the professional academicians. The commonalities among all these models were further investigated in order to develop a convenient, best fitted and advanced model for training Higher Education Academicians, most probably can be utilised to train the general education teachers or school teachers.

Keywords: Training Models, FDTs, Teaching Competencies, Pedagogic Skills and Competencies Specific Faculty Development Training Model (CSFDTM).

Introduction

In this ever changing and challenging environment of higher Education, "one of the obligations of University leadership is to choose to grow its staff professionally so as to support learning and improve student performance" (Bank and Mayes, 2001). The need and importance of Faculty Development Training (FDP) in education is almost axiomatic. (Rebecca Brent, Richard M. Felder, Intl. Journal of Engg. Education, 19 (2), 234–240 (2003). So Faculty Development Trainings (FDTs) had become utmost important in this era of knowledge society whereas only few remarkable and complete Faculty Development Training Models (FDTMs) could be recognised to develop the Pedagogic Skills and Teaching Competencies of Higher Education Academicians. Pedagogy Training should be the part and parcel of job for higher education teachers because they were not exposed to any professional educational Training before starting their career as a teacher unlike the school teachers. The American Heritage® Dictionary of English Language defines pedagogy as "The art or profession of teaching". The operational definition, "Pedagogy is the art and science of instruction for the purpose of leading the pupil towards desired educational goal". According to Postareff et al. (2007), teacher has little knowledge of pedagogy in higher educational setting, if any formal systematic professional training in teaching other than the content of their discipline may improve their pedagogical skill. In any kind of research study, it is necessary to acquaint one with what has already been thought, expressed and undertaken about the problem under investigation. So researcher investigated various training models for training Higher Education Academicians. Fuller (1970) developed a model which is one of the first model to identify the stages of changes that teachers pass through during their developmental process it is applicable for the teachers of all sectors. This

model is more or less same as Kember, (1997) and Akerlind, (2003) model of teacher’s training and development. Ekbote (1987) studied the integration of teaching skills with instructional material, teaching technology and other software in a typical teacher-training programme in` India and developed a workable model which can be easily utilised in any Indian teacher training centre or institute.Nyquist and Wulff (1996) identified the stages of development of beginning teachers at the University of Washington and provided a general coherent model which assists the newly appointed teachers to develop their teaching skills and pedagogy competency.

According to Dessler (1991), the training program ideally involves four steps, which are explained with the help of diagram as mentioned in figure 1.1. In this, the first step is the assessment step to identify the performance deficiency that could be control out of training. The second step consists of the training objectives, follows whether there are one or more competency deficiencies which might be filled through training. The third step is the training step, in which the actual training techniques and methods are chosen and finally implemented. The last step involves the evaluation step, here the trainees’ pre and post training competencies and performances are compared and the effectiveness of the training program is thus evaluated by means of trainees’ reaction, perceptions, learning behaviour or performance results.

Figure 1.1: The Dessler’s Training Model (1991)

Richey (1992)gave another remarkable model for teacher’s training and development as an Input, Process and Output Model (Fig 1.2) where training outcomes are input from the learners and the environment. The design and delivery characteristics of training formed the process. Output of the model includes changes in competency accumulation of the learner. This model reflects the casual relationships between these inputs and outputs.

Figure 1.2: The Richey’s Training Model 1992

As Goldstein, (1993) has also mentioned that Training approaches generally needs to have appropriate system to achieve the desired goal. To achieve this goal the Training system involves three main functions: (1) Input: A venue, training materials, higher level academicians, proficient and experienced trainer, required money and resources. (2) Process: Correct procedure and technique, lecture practice, required time and environment etc. and (3) Output: Improved attitude, Measurable changes in the behaviour of all trainees and all together Improvement in the competency of the teacher trainees (knowledge, skill and attitude improvements) mentioned in figure 1.3

Figure 1.3: The Goldstein Model 1993

Kugel (1993) proposed an Advanced Teacher’s Development Model which specifically focuses on the changes that take place in Higher Education Academicians. The early stages of models are characterised by focusing on self and knowledge of the subject with a transition to focus on the skills and the process of teaching and finally emphasised on student’s learning. Kugel’s model is slightly more involved as it unpicks the process of teachers’ centric and increased focus on the student’s learning. Kugel’s three stages of development: where the focus is upon the students but in moderately different ways; a focus was upon the student as *receptive*, *active* and *independent*. Nyquist and Wulff (1996) models also appear to be strikingly similar to Kugel’s model and also similar to the earlier more Generic Model, developed by Fuller. There are some other studies that provide a better insight into how an individual may learn to teach in higher education.

Nadler’s Training Model (1994) comprises of the series of steps called “event” that provides the trainer straight forward, easy-to-follow system for designing training program to improve performance and efficiency at job. It includes the need assessment of the job and individual that necessitates training, involve supervisors to manage the training, obtain required resources for training and use specific instructional methods and strategies. An evaluation and feedback session is being done at the last, reflected in Figure 1.4.

1

Chang (1995) introduced ‘The High Impact Training Model ‘which comprises of six steps of training, where all steps are connected to each other and followed each step for its application as a process like, the first step start with identifying the training needs and expectations, second step includes mapping the approach, the third step induces learning tools, the fourth step uses different training techniques, the fifth step consists of calculating the measurable results and finally the six step, the follow up step is taken for corrective action.

Gagne and Medsker (1996) provided a summary of how the system approaches are different from the “traditional” or non system approaches to training. As the traditional approach to training does not follow the set procedure and provideunreliable feedback. On the other hand “Training as a system implies those goals and objectives drive all other components and decisions associated with the training and that of feedback from all parts of the training process is used to correct all other aspects of the process.”

Figure 1.6: The Gagne and Medsker’s Training Model 1996

Kember (1997) reviews thirteen studies separately to represent a model which categorized these studies within which the conceptions of teaching can be considered. The model represents two main orientations, first is basically teacher-driven and transmits the content, and the second predominantly focuses on the students and provide learning that ensued. These two orientations provide two sub-conceptions ways of experiencing teaching. First depicts the concepts that are correlated to conceptual change and intellectual or logical development of the students. This is a conceptual model, related to teachers imparting knowledge and skills to their students and in which students were not considered as passive recipients of the subject matter. He standardized this as *student-teacher interaction* where the teacher understands the importance of interactions between themselves and the students. He referred this as an intermediate category and termed as ‘transitional’.

Figure 1.7: The Kember's Model on Training on Conception of Teaching

Casio (1998) introduced a general system model of training and development includes three steps process as follows: Assessment, Training and Development and Evaluation. In the Casio model, the first step as the analysis of need, serves as a foundation for entire training efforts. This training model includes both the training and development phase and the evaluation phase, depends on need assessment. The need assessment phase is to determine what teacher needs to learn in relation to desire teaching and learning behaviour. If this phase is not tactfully analyzed, the whole training program remains unproductive. The objectives of the training program should be carefully set; the next task is to create the environment in which these objectives can be achieved. Evaluation process includes two phases; as establishing the indicators of success at training and at work place and other; determining exactly what job related changes have occurred as a result of training. Evaluation of training should be a continuous process to provide feedback, can be utilized to fulfil the training needs.

Figure 1.8: The Casio's Model on Training and Learning (1998)

Prosser and Trigwell (1999) have presented a model based on Kember's Model (1997) to reflect the various elements, which have been recognized important in 'student learning' research domain and their dependency on each other as represented in the diagram 1.9. This model focuses on teaching in higher education which is basically concern for the *approaches* of teaching. The findings, with regards to conceptions and approaches to teaching and training, derived from phenomenal analysis of data collected through interviews, conducted with twenty-four University science teachers, resultant six categories were identified which were very much similar to those, identified by the Kember (1997).

Figure 1.9: The Prosser and Trigwell's Model for Training on Teaching and Learning

Samithikrai (1999) introduced 'A Systematic Training Model' where importance was given to systematic thinking; it basically focus on the relation among the factors and the continuous changes in the system. Numerous steps have been taken under this training model, reflected in model number 1.10

Figure 1.10: The Smithikrai's Model on Training (1999)

Bangmo (2001) stated that Faculty Development Training Model (FDTM) is strategic plan of the whole program which is designed to improve performance at individual, group as well as at organizational level. This in turn implies the measurable changes in knowledge, skills, attitudes and behaviour of the teacher trainees. According to Bangmo, systematic training includes 5 factors; Input: A venue, faculty, knowledgeable and experienced trainers, required material and resources (financial and material). Process: To Prepare Lecture, presentation skills, practice, time, environment for training etc. Output: measurable improvement in the level of competencies (skills, knowledge, attitude and behaviour) of the teacher trainees. Feedback: To check the effectiveness and achievement of the training; whether the trained trainees have changed their behaviour according to pre-decided goal. Environment: To evaluate competition, organizations' social laws and cultural advancement. He added two more steps in his model Feedback and Environment which were not so very common in the earlier models.

Rao's (2001), Model of Training caters the need of science and technology teachers including the professional educators. Rao's strategy of training teachers demonstrated through diagram 1.11;

Figure 1.11: The Rao's Model on Training (2001)

The IPST Model for Training (Burns, 2011): The institute for the Promotion of the Teaching of Science and Technology (IPST) trained the science teacher; usually utilize a systematic approach with high proficiency and expertise; however they do not draw any conclusion in term of model. After the intensive study of this approach and interviews conducted with the expert in the IPST and also after going through some of their training sessions & presentation by their experts, these approaches can be divided into 5 steps as demonstrated in the flow chart (Fig 1.12).

Figure 1.12: The IPST Model for Training

These models build professional learning communities in which teachers; “enlisting colleagues to help them critique and improve implementation of a particular idea or strategy and customize, personalize and adapt new skills and concepts to their particular setting” (Burns, 2011: 190).

Commonalities between all the Models: The identification of competencies deficiencies, deciding the training objectives, arranging the required materials and resources, implementation of training and its evaluation are the common steps to maximum training models like Dessler model (1992), Reley (1992), Kugal (1993), Nadler (1994), Chag (1995) , Gagny and Madsker (1996), Casio (1998), Smithikrai (1999) and the IPST Model (Burns, 2011). Almost all models were explained under three stages Input, Process and Output. Desseler, Reley, Kugal, Bangmo and Cassio explained their model in process involving various steps in sequence for providing training to their trainees but Nadler and Gagny and Medskar models involve almost all the steps and differentiated between traditional and modern approaches to teacher’s trainings. Prosser and Trigwell (1997) presented an advanced model, based on Kamber’s Model of teachers’ training which highlights the conceptions and approaches to teaching and learning. Kugel and Smithikrai models are more systematic models to cater the need of teacher trainees. Kember reviewed thirteen modern models and gave a new advanced model for teachers’ training consisting of two main orientation- teachers driven and students centric which has been introduced in various teacher trainings module.

A Complete Competencies Specific Faculty Development Training Model (CSFDTM) for Higher Education Teachers:

After conducting the in depth review of available literature and extensive analysis of teachers’ training models and approaches the researcher decided to prepare a competency specific faculty development training models for Higher Education Teachers. This model includes the various steps to be taken a head to train the teachers. Which have been reflected in the model (1.13).The first and foremost steps is to conduct asurvey to identify and analyse a Problem regarding the teaching competency of teachers than need assessment of roles and responsibilities is done in order to determine the training objectives. After doing the need assessment of job,

trainer tries to identify the nature and characteristics of trainees and institutional environment and than required material and resources are collected to introduced and implement learning tools, methods and techniques and then curriculum are set. After formulating all the strategies trainers are in position to impart training with complete enthusiasm and inner motivation. After delivery of training its effectiveness is measure with the help of evaluation and follow up to compare the the level of competence whether it is developed according to the pre decided objectives or not, so that corrective action can be undertaken finally to validate the results.

1.3: A Competency Specific Model for Higher Education Academicians

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